

Complexes of Molybdenum(III) with 2-(2'-Pyridyl) Benzimidazole

S. P. GHOSH*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

and

K. M. PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, H. D. Jain College, Arrah-802 301

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Molybdenum(III) forms with 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole (LH) the trischelated complexes, $[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3]\text{X}_3$, as well as the cationic-anionic complexes, $[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3\text{X}_2]^+$ $[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})\text{X}_4]^-$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-$ or NCS^-), depending on pH. These complexes have been synthesised and characterised from elemental analyses, i.r. and electronic spectra, magnetic moments and molar conductance.

COMPLEX compounds of 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole(I) is of interest because of the biologically important imidazole grouping present in it. This ligand, unlike 2-2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline, is more flexible due to the absence of one α -hydrogen and forms five membered chelate ring. Ghosh *et al.*¹⁻³ have investigated the complexes of this ligand with several transition elements. Complexes of molybdenum(III) are now reported.

Experimental

All preparative work was carried out in an atmosphere of purified dry nitrogen.

Materials : The ammonium salts of pentachloro-aquomolybdate(III), pentabromo-aquomolybdate(III) and hexa isothiocyanatomolybdate(III) were prepared by the electrolysis of ammonium (para) molybdate in (8N) HCl, 48% HBr and dil. H_2SO_4 respectively⁴⁻⁶.

The ligand was prepared by the condensation of α -picolinic acid with *o*-phenylenediamine⁷.

Physical Measurements : Conductivity measurements were made with a WTW Conductivity Bridge, type LBR. Magnetic moments were determined with a Gouy magnetic balance, making diamagnetic corrections using Pascal's constants⁸. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a Hilger and Watts Uvispek spectrophotometer H 700 with a standard reflectance attachment with magnesium carbonate as reference. I.R. spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer 237 Infrared spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Complexes :

$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3]\text{Cl}_3$: 0.84 g of ammonium pentachloro-aquomolybdate(III) was allowed to react with a methanolic solution of the ligand (1 g) with constant stirring. The chloro-aquo complex gradually dissolved and a deep-violet solution was obtained. It was filtered; the filtrate deposited violet-red crystals. These were washed with benzene and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 and KOH.

$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3]\text{Br}_3$: The above method of preparation was followed with the use of ammonium pentabromo-aquomolybdate(III) instead of the chloro-aquo complex. The violet-red crystals obtained were dried in vacuum over KOH/ CaCl_2 .

$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3](\text{NCS})_3$: This compound was obtained by the reaction of the ligand (1 g) and $(\text{NH}_4)_3[\text{Mo}(\text{NCS})_6]$ (0.84 g) in methanol. The reaction mixture was kept at 50-60° for 30 minutes. On cooling in an icebath, sparingly soluble violet-red crystals separated. These were filtered, washed with minimum volume of ethanol and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 and KOH.

$\text{Mo}_2\text{Cl}_6(\text{LH})_3$: Ammonium pentachloro-aquomolybdate(III) (1 g) was dissolved in 15 ml water : 7.5 ml HCl (10M) : 7.5 ml ethanol (2 : 1 : 1) mixture. A solution of the ligand (1.7 g) in 10 ml ethanol was gradually added to the above solution. The reaction mixture was gently stirred at room temperature by a slow current of nitrogen. After about 5 hours it was concentrated to half its volume, under reduced pressure on a steambath. The dark-red product which separated on cooling was stable in air. It was filtered off, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in vacuum over KOH/ CaCl_2 .

$\text{Mo}_2\text{Br}_6(\text{LH})_3$: This was obtained as above by using $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoBr}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ in aqueous ethanolic hydrobromic acid. The dark-red product was dried in vacuum over KOH/CaCl_2 .

$\text{Mo}_2(\text{NCS})_6(\text{LH})_3$: This compound obtained as a deep-red solid when methanolic solution of $\text{Mo}_2\text{Cl}_6(\text{LH})_3$ 1.5 g (1 mole) and 0.7 g (6 mole) of ammonium thiocyanate were refluxed on a steambath for 6 hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen. It was filtered and dried in vacuum over KOH/CaCl_2 .

Results and Discussion

Under the experimental condition used, it appears that ammonium salt of pentachloroaquomolybdate(III), pentabromo-aquomolybdate(III) or hexa-isothiocyanatomolybdate(III) can be easily substituted by this chelating ligand at pH 7. The resulting complexes can be formulated as $[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3]\text{X}_3$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- or NCS^-). Under specific pH and solvent conditions as reported by Carmichael *et al*⁹ (pH 3-5) the cationic-anionic complexes $[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_2\text{X}_3]^+$ $[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})\text{X}_4]^-$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$ or Br^-) is produced from pentahalogenoaquomolybdate(III). The deep-red crystals of $[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]^+$ $[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})(\text{NCS})_4]^-$ were obtained by refluxing the above salt-like, mixed chloro-complex with ammonium thiocyanate in 95% methanol.

Attempts to prepare different salts of the trischelated complex cations with aqueous methanolic solutions of silver nitrate and perchlorate were unsuccessful and instead, a shining mirror of silver was formed due to the reduction of Ag^+ ion by molybdenum(III).

All the complexes are fairly stable in air. The trischelated complexes are completely soluble in methanol whereas the complexes $\text{Mo}_2\text{X}_6(\text{LH})_3$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- or NCS^-) are almost insoluble in methanol. The electrical conductance of trischelated complexes in anhydrous methanol, nearly correspond with the values expected for a 1 : 3 electrolyte (Table 1). The molar conductance values of the complexes $\text{Mo}_2\text{X}_6(\text{LH})_3$ are in agreement with 1 : 1 electrolyte in DMF solvent¹⁰.

The effective magnetic moments (Table 1) calculated per atom of molybdenum of all the complexes fall within the range 3.64-3.73 B.M. expected for octahedral molybdenum(III) complexes¹¹, suggesting no interaction between the two Mo(III) ions.

The transitions (cm^{-1}) in the diffuse reflectance spectra of the complexes are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Compound	$^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$	$^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}$	$^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}$
$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3]\text{Cl}_3$	18868 bs	23810 s	25641 s
$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3]\text{Br}_3$	19231 bs	22222 m	25000 s
$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3](\text{NCS})_3$	18519 bs	23256 m	26178 m
$\text{Mo}_2\text{Cl}_6(\text{LH})_3$	14706 m	19608 bm	23810 m
$\text{Mo}_2\text{Br}_6(\text{LH})_3$	14925 bm	20000 m	24390 m
$\text{Mo}_2(\text{NCS})_6(\text{LH})_3$	—	—	24520 s

m=medium, s=strong, b=broad.

The complexes exhibit the expected three maxima within the range 14000-26000 cm^{-1} ¹². The electronic spectra of pentahalogenoaquomolybdate(III) have been reported earlier by us¹³. The chelated complexes show a hypsochromic shift of the three spin allowed bands. This can be correlated with the higher position which N-bonding 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole occupies relative to Cl^- , Br^- or NCS^- in the spectrochemical series. The transitions involved are confined to the levels arising from the t_{2g}^3 configuration of Oh symmetry, and, in the simple ligand-field approximation, depend upon the interelectronic repulsion parameters only¹⁴. Since symmetry effects appear to be fairly small, the interelectronic repulsions must be reduced as substitution with 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole proceeds. This could be taken as evidence for increased metal-ligand π -bonding, as would be expected when Cl^- , Br^- or NCS^- is replaced by the ligand 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole. The d-d transitions in $(\text{NH}_4)_3[\text{Mo}(\text{NCS})_6]$ are obscured by intense charge transfer absorption in the region¹⁵: but the complex $\text{Mo}_2(\text{NCS})_6(\text{LH})_3$ exhibit one d-d band at 24520 cm^{-1} . The other d-d bands are enveloped by charge transfer tail.

TABLE 1*—ANALYTICAL RESULTS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND EFFECTIVE MAGNETIC MOMENTS (AT 300°K)

Compound	Mo(%)		Cl(%)		H(%)		N(%)		Anion(%)		Conductance $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ M in solvent a or b)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3]\text{Cl}_3$	12.15	12.19	54.67	54.85	3.48	3.43	16.10	16.0	13.48	13.52	253.0a	3.71
$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3]\text{Br}_3$	10.46	10.42	46.78	46.90	3.02	2.93	13.65	13.68	26.12	26.05	247.5a	3.68
$[\text{Mo}(\text{LH})_3](\text{NCS})_3$	11.24	11.23	54.65	54.73	3.21	3.15	19.66	19.64	—	—	248.0a	3.64
$\text{Mo}_2\text{Cl}_6(\text{LH})_3$	19.18	19.39	44.32	43.64	2.73	2.72	12.72	12.73	21.46	21.51	70.5b	3.69
$\text{Mo}_2\text{Br}_6(\text{LH})_3$	15.30	15.27	34.45	34.86	2.16	2.14	10.11	10.02	38.24	38.18	72.0b	3.64
$\text{Mo}_2(\text{NCS})_6(\text{LH})_3$	17.04	17.06	44.63	44.80	2.46	2.40	18.57	18.66	—	—	73.5b	3.73

* Molar conductance, at 25°, a in methanol, b in DMF, 1 B.M. $\approx 9.27 \times 10^{-24}$ Am².

A comparison of the i.r. spectrum of 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole with those of its trischelated and cationic-anionic complexes shows very little change in frequencies in the region (1428-2000 cm^{-1}) due to chelation. This may be due to the presence of the aromatic rings in these compounds, which allows greater coupling and conjugation. The slight increase (10-18 cm^{-1}) on chelation, in the frequency of pyridine breathing vibration of medium intensity 996 cm^{-1} is in accordance with the previous observations¹⁶. The N-H stretching frequency of the ligand in the solid state is found to be 3247 cm^{-1} whereas, in dilute chloroform solution, the peak position changes to 3430 cm^{-1} . The lowering of the frequency in the solid state can be attributed to intermolecular hydrogen bonding. In trischelated and cationic-anionic complexes of Mo(III), the N-H stretching frequency shifts to 3200-3000 cm^{-1} . Since coordination does not take place through the iminonitrogen, the lowering of the N-H stretching frequency in these complexes can be explained by the resonance structures (A) and (B)¹⁷.

Donation of the pair of electrons from the unsaturated nitrogen to the metal ion would increase the contribution of (B) resulting in a lowering of the N-H stretching frequency.

In the case of ammonium hexa isothiocyanato-molybdate(III) the ν_{CN} and ν_{CS} are recorded at 2090 and 810 cm^{-1} respectively. The complex $\text{Mo}_2(\text{NCS})_6(\text{LH})_3$ exhibits only one strong CN stretching band at 2085 cm^{-1} and a weak CS stretching band at 815 cm^{-1} which are diagnostic of N-bonded thiocyanate¹⁸. As there is no splitting of the CN stretching band in $\text{Mo}_2(\text{NCS})_6(\text{LH})_3$,

it may be inferred that all NCS are equivalent, having a trans configuration¹⁹.

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